

THE NETWORK TASKING ORDER (NTO)

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ABSTRACT

Information and network communications play a vital role in the everyday operations of the United States Armed Forces. As the Department of Defense moves more toward Net-Centric Warfare, this role will only increase. Traditional work in Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks (MANETs) assumes there is no knowledge available about mobility patterns or communication traffic over time. However, this is generally not the case in military networks. In this article, we put forward the notion of a Network Tasking Order (NTO), which exploits a priori knowledge of network characteristics such as required data input/output, communications capability, and communications capacity. The concept of an NTO is defined as a parallel to the Air Tasking Order (ATO). Our premise is that the knowledge in an NTO can be used to achieve greater network reliability, to attain better network management, and to assist in optimizing network topology and routing. We present a scenario in which, based upon information contained in an NTO, low priority messages are either redirected or scaled back to avoid having high priority messages dropped from the network.

MOTIVATION

Department of Defense (DoD) Directive 8100.1 [1] defines the Global Information Grid (GIG) as the “globally interconnected, end-to-end set of information capabilities, associated processes, and personnel for collecting, processing, storing, disseminating and managing information on demand to warfighters, policy makers, and support personnel.” In particular, the GIG includes all equipment involved in the transfer of information, that is, the military communications network. *Joint Vision (JV) 2020* [2] specifies that the GIG will provide the network-centric environment needed to achieve the goal of a US military that is a joint force capable of full spectrum dominance. In more current parlance, the future GIG will enable net-centric warfare/net-centric operations (NCW/NCO). In *DoD GIG Architectural Vision* [3], the current GIG is described as static rather than dynamic and incapable of supporting NCW/NCO. Much research and

work is required to ensure that communications, computing, and information infrastructures can respond to rapidly changing operational needs. In doing so, a level of quality of service (QoS) must be provided. As DoD Chief Information Officer, John G. Grimes, states it in the preface to [3], “ensuring timely and trusted information is available where it is needed, when it is needed, and to those who need it is at the heart of net-centricity.” Information needs to move to where it is needed, whether it is localized from soldier to soldier on the battlefield or worldwide from soldier to decision makers. Information needs to move reliably and quickly. The loss or delay of information can literally result in the difference between life and death.

BACKGROUND

One large factor in designing the future GIG is to understand the types of technologies that it will employ. As the DoD makes a transition to NCW/NCO, an increasing percentage of nodes in the network will be mobile, and necessarily wireless. In addition, there will likely be little existing infrastructure with which to connect. Thus, portions of the network will take the form of a mobile ad-hoc network (MANET). With the advent of IPv6, we expect each asset and person will be a node in the network. The mobile assets include the aircraft, ships, and ground vehicles, both manned and unmanned; as well as various satellites and individual munitions. There are also static assets such as satellites in geosynchronous orbits, individual workstations both deployed or at home, and sensors. Personnel become nodes in the network when they are wearing networked equipment like video sharing night vision helmets or sensors monitoring information such as location, health condition, or perception of the threat space to assist in achieving a Common Operational Picture.

Typically, most MANETs utilize omni-directional antennae and communicate using the ad-hoc implementation of the IEEE 802.11x protocol. However, this protocol has bandwidth (54 Mbps) and scalability problems which limit its use in a deployed military environment. IEEE 802.11 cannot support a large-scale ad hoc network [4]. A more realistic network design for NCW/NCO includes directional wireless technology, such as free space optical (FSO) or directed radio frequency (RF) devices, in addition to the omni-directional devices. This combination of technologies forms a hybrid-MANET

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(H-MANET). While controlling the topology of a network containing directional links is known to be NP-hard [5], advances have been made to developing heuristics that quickly calculate solutions to facilitate H-MANETs in dynamic environments [6-8]. H-MANETs are likely to play an increasing role in future military mission.

The usual mobility assumptions made when researching ad hoc networks do not apply in the NCW/NCO framework. Due to the prohibitive cost of performing research with real networks, the majority of research uses simulations to generate results. Underlying these simulations is a choice of mobility model for directing the movement of the nodes. The most commonly used mobility models are the random walk or the random waypoint models [9, 10]. There are also various extensions such as non-uniform waypoint distribution, random waypoint on border model, etc. These models all either assume random positioning of nodes, random movement of nodes, or both. Even with models like the city section mobility model that severely restrict the traveling behavior of a mobile node, the random aspect of the model only allows for a probabilistic analysis of topology and routing. One can only say that there is a certain chance that a node will be in a particular position. Another widely used assumption is that the environment is two-dimensional. Military operations can involve worldwide communications (operators stateside controlling UAVs overseas). In addition, assets are located on the ground, in the air, and in orbit. There also exist obstacles to communications such as buildings, mountains, or the Earth itself. While there will always be some degree of randomness in the location of a mobile node, in a military scenario we can take advantage of the highly planned nature of proceedings.

The daily schedule of air related operations is documented in the Air Tasking Order (ATO). The ATO is a human/machine readable document that is used to task air missions. Among many other things, the ATO includes a list of types and number of aircraft, mission types, routes (including time and position), target locations, positions of friendly forces, cryptography codes in use, and frequencies being used. In addition, there is a free text area where specific communications plans can be placed. The information contained within an ATO can be paired with a database of information such as the networking capabilities of each asset. From this pairing, a daily schedule for the network, similar to the ATO, a so-called Network Tasking Order (NTO), could be created. It should be possible to achieve greater network reliability and predictability through the information collated into an NTO.

The idea of an NTO is not new. In a 2006 white paper [11], Ranne and McKee advocate that United States Strategic

Command's Joint Task Force – Global Network Operations and/or Air Force Network Operations conduct concept and prototype development with GIG NetOps Tasking Orders for command and control of the GIG. The concept of an NTO has appeared in several theses at the Air Force Institute of Technology. In [12], Stookey provides background and data to build a notional battlespace for testing and simulating the use of dynamic networks within the US military. Stookey elaborates on the necessity of developing an NTO to provide dynamic network routers a basis for making predictive decisions about where given nodes are spatially in a battlespace, what data links might be available, the bandwidth or throughput of such links, the bandwidth requirements of various data flows, and the priority of the data that might be destined to or coming from various nodes. In [13], Pecarina envisions an NTO in which a Joint Forces Cyber Component Commander could assign weights of effort to different mission goals in cyberspace. In addition, he sees the NTO as a means of addressing the flip side of the QoS coin mentioned above. The NTO will help to move to a point where unimportant information that wastes time, bandwidth, and energy is blocked to allow the critical data to get through. Finally, the 50th Network Ops Group at Shriever AFB publishes a daily network tasking order to assist in allowing command and control of the Air Force Satellite Control Network which includes the Defense Support Program, the Navstar Global Positioning System, the Defense Satellite Communications System, NATO III, and Milstar. This schedule makes sure the satellite fliers have the needed ground antenna resources to perform routine tasks and to perform telemetry and other data transfers [14].

In this paper, we intend to show through simulation that the NTO has the potential to improve network reliability. We believe this to be a fundamental first step that has yet to be performed. It is rather easy to envision scenarios in which an NTO *should* increase reliability and can help with the task of optimizing network topology and routing. However, we have not found any experiments in the course of our research that have been performed to specifically support this claim. But first, we will go into some more detail about what the NTO could look like.

NETWORK TASKING ORDER SPECIFICS

Material contained in the NTO

The information in this section is taken from the United States Message Text Format Message Browser [15]. All of the missions in the ATO are grouped first by tasked country, then by tasked service, and after that by individual tasked units. It makes sense to keep this structure in an NTO so that the units that own each network component can easily find the pieces they are responsible for and

configure them for the planned day. In addition, it is possible that communications will exist between the asset and its home unit that need to be planned for.

Once the ATO gets down to the individual unit level, all missions that unit are responsible for appear sequentially. Within each mission, the number and type of aircraft along with call sign and primary configuration are given. In addition, the following information may also be given: secondary configuration codes, Link 16 abbreviated call sign, Tactical Air Navigation system channel, primary Joint Tactical Information Distribution System Unit address, and identification friend or foe/selective identification feature (IFF/SIF) mode and code.

There may be differences in networking capabilities between two aircraft of the same type. The capabilities of an F-16 from one unit could be radically different from those of an F-16 from another unit. However, within a single unit, the differences should be minimal. It would be useful to develop a baseline capability for each aircraft type for each unit. A minimal set of data should include:

- Number and types of interfaces (FSO, RF, etc.)
- Transmission speed/range
- Encryption capability
- Accepted protocols
- Set-up time
- Queue characteristics

This information should be kept in a single database so that when a unit/asset pair is given, the networking capabilities of that asset can be automatically entered into the NTO. To the best of our knowledge, no all-inclusive database containing this information currently exists. Though likely classified, it ought to be fairly straightforward to compile such a database. Over time, revisions to the database could be accomplished by program offices or depots.

Missions in the ATO usually include a route with altitudes and speeds. Routes can either be a round trip to a target location with departure/return locations and times, one-way travel with departure/arrival locations and times, or orbit information with departure/return locations and times. In any case, given this information, we have some general idea of where an aircraft is going to be and when it will be there. When satellites or aircraft fly over for limited but predictable time spans, the utilization of these resources can be planned for ahead of time. For example, a directional antenna can be prepositioned to the expected pointing angle so that it is ready for service when needed. Thus some simplified version of this information should be included in the NTO.

Each mission has a preferred mission type or designation. Mission type does not necessarily need to go into the NTO, but it may give a clue as to the type of traffic. For example, a combat search and rescue mission probably has different traffic characteristics than air reconnaissance or aerial refueling. The expected quantity and burstiness of traffic flows are important measures to include in the NTO.

By including the priority of certain traffic flows, routing agents can use this information to make decisions in situations of congestion. The agents can decide to allow the high priority information to pass through while dropping or delaying the lower priority information. Another alternative is directing information over different routes or storing information to send at times of lower activity. Missions in the ATO are given priorities, and one can generally assume the transmissions of a mission of high priority would also have high priority. Thus, it will be imperative to carry these priorities into the NTO to allow for ranking of traffic flows.

Creation process for the NTO

ATOs follow a three-day life cycle. On any given day, the next day's ATO is being planned, the current day's ATO is being executed, and the previous day's ATO is being assessed. The NTO process should closely follow, or be done in unison with the ATO process because the network is there to support the missions. Any changes made to the ATO during execution should likewise be reflected in the NTO. The missions need to be known in order to plan the network. However, the process of creating the NTO can add insight that might result in changes to the ATO.

By having a plan in place, it becomes more apparent where there could be single points of failure, gaps in connectivity, or bottlenecks. In such cases, it might be possible to change an orbit or add an extra asset. For example, one waypoint of an E-3's orbit could be adjusted slightly to allow periodic high bandwidth line-of-sight communications to a ground unit that would otherwise be plagued with constant low bandwidth connections. Another example could be the addition of a communications relay mission for a UAV to linger over a certain location to act as a wireless router in support of a high priority mission.

Notional Example

We conclude this section by providing a simple example of what a translation of a single mission from an ATO into an NTO might look like. We emphasize that the information here is made-up and does not represent any real mission.

In the ATO, each line of data is terminated by '/', however due to length may wrap to fill multiple lines of text. Below are a few lines from an ATO that pertain to a single mission:

```
TSKCNTRY/US//  
SVCTASK/F//  
TASKUNIT/23FS/ICAO:ETAD//  
AMSNDAT/N/D123HB/-/-/SEAD/-/-/DEPLOC:KGZ6/  
241200ZAPR/ARRLOC:KDZ7/241300ZAPR//  
MSNACFT/1/ACTYP:F16CJ/SUPP01/2HARM/-/20001/30111//  
AMSNLOC/-/-/210/1//
```

The first three lines detail what is being tasked. Here, the country is the US, the service is the Air Force, and the unit is the 23rd Fighter Squadron at Spangdahlem Air Base (ETAD). In the fourth line, AMSNDAT stands for aircraft mission data, and it is followed by twelve fields. Fields containing ‘-’ are optional and no data has been entered. In the first field, the ‘N’ indicates that the mission is non-residual; it falls entirely within the ATO period. The mission number is D123HB. The primary mission type is Suppression of Enemy Air Defenses (SEAD). The mission departs from location KGZ6 on 24 April at 1200Z and arrives at location KDZ7 on 24 April at 1300Z. In the fifth line, MSNACFT stands for individual aircraft mission data, and it is followed by seven fields. The first three fields specify the mission is comprised of one F16-CJ Fighting Falcon with call sign ‘SUPP01’. In the primary configuration field, ‘2HARM’ indicates the aircraft should be equipped with two AGM-88 high-speed anti-radiation missiles. The 20001 and 30111 are mode two and three IFF/SIF codes. The last line gives additional mission location information; here, an altitude of 210 hundred feet and a mission priority of 1.

In the NTO we could have the following corresponding lines:

```
TSKNODE/US/F/23FS/LATM:4960N0642E//  
NODETYP/F16CJ/SEAD/AVE:5KBPS/BURST:15KBPS/1//  
IFACE/1/IDM-302/16KBPS//  
NODELOC/210/LATM:5044N0706E /241200ZAPR/  
LATM:5122N0728E /241300ZAPR//
```

The first line combines the country, service, and unit information. Note that the ICAO code for Spangdahlem AB is replaced with latitude/longitude information. The second line describes the node type and its mission. Based upon the mission type, the expected data rate of average and bursty communications are provided. Finally, the mission priority is added to this line as well. The third line shows information that could be pulled from the capabilities database. Here, the NTO indicates that the aircraft has one Improved Data Modem (IDM-302) which is capable of 16 kbps digital communications. The last line includes the altitude followed by a list of node locations. This list comprises alternating fields of latitudes/longitudes and times. Here, we only know the starting and ending locations of the node, but for missions that have waypoints,

the list can be longer. Again, note that location codes have been replaced with latitudes/longitudes.

SIMULATION

We now describe two related scenarios which show how *a priori* knowledge of network conditions through an NTO can be exploited to improve the QoS of a network.

Scenarios

Both scenarios consist of two sources generating information that needs to be sent to a common destination. The destination is far enough away that direct communication is not available, but there is an intermediate node that can act as a router. Both sources have a 36 kbps connection to the router, and the router has a 36 kbps connection to the destination. Source 1, perhaps a UAV with a video feed, will produce high-priority data at a rate of 30.6 kbps over a thirty-minute time span starting at some time between 1400 and 1500. Source 2 is continually generating data at a rate of 7.2 kbps, but the data is of low priority and not time-sensitive. Perhaps the data from source 2 is collated and reviewed once daily. Suppose that, an E-8 Joint Surveillance and Target Attack Radar System (JSTARS) or an E-3 Sentry (AWACS) aircraft is flying a 30-minute orbit located between source 2 and the destination from 1300 to 1800. This particular aircraft is known to be carrying equipment that allows wireless line-of-sight networking at a capacity of 28.8 kbps. The orbit is such that it is only in line-of-sight of source 2 for 10 minutes, it is only in line-of-sight with the destination for 10 minutes, and there is no overlap in these time spans. Thus, the aircraft cannot act as a router. However, the aircraft can be used as a data ferry, storing the information that is uploaded from source 2 and downloading it later to the destination when it is in range.

In the first scenario, we examine what might happen without an NTO for guidance. Given the choice between sending its traffic to the router or to the aircraft, the operators for source 2 may opt to send its traffic through the router over the 36 kbps link. This seems like a reasonable choice given the larger bandwidth of this route and the delay that would be associated with data ferrying. However, the operators for source 2 are likely not aware that there will be a 30-minute period where source 1 is also sending data through the router. In addition, without an NTO, the router itself has no knowledge of the relative priorities of messages coming from source 1 and source 2. Even if the router is using a protocol such as Differentiated Services, source 1 and source 2 have not been directed what forwarding behaviors to put in their packet headers. This scenario is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Scenario without an NTO

In the second scenario, we examine what might happen with the existence of an NTO. While creating the NTO, the conflict between source 1 and source 2 is exposed. Since it is known that the information from source 2 is not time-sensitive, the delay associated with data ferrying is tolerable. Furthermore, contention for queue space at the router could cause high-priority packets from source 1 to be dropped. Since the information from source 2 is of lower priority, it is decided that the traffic from source 2 should be sent to the aircraft for the period from 1400 to 1500. This decision is made at the operational level and given as a directive to the operators of source 2 (and also of the aircraft) through the NTO. The increase in end-to-end delay for source 2 is justified by the increased reliability of the overall network. This scenario is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Scenario with an NTO

Design of Experiments

Both scenarios are modeled in NS-2, with each simulation covering a time span of one hour. The metric we are interested in capturing is percentage of dropped packets for both sources. We assume propagation delay is negligible and consider only transmission, queuing, and ferrying

delays. All sources will use UDP agents generating constant bit rate traffic. For both scenarios, source 1 produces traffic from 1410 to 1440, while source 2 generates traffic for the full hour.

For scenario 1, we have source 2 sending 7.2 kbps and source 1 sending 30.6 kbps of information as it is generated through the router from 1400 to 1500. These rates can be produced in many ways by adjusting packet size and the interval between packets. One extreme is for source 1 to send a 3825-byte packet once per second and for source 2 to send a 900-byte packet once per second. To make the simulation more realistic, we consider packet sizes of 8 bytes through 64 bytes in steps of 8 bytes for both sources. The time interval between packets will be adjusted accordingly.

For scenario 2, source 2 needs to send 30-minutes worth of data within a ten-minute window of opportunity. To allow some room for connections to be established between the airplane and source 2, we arrange for the data to be sent in only eight minutes. Thus 12.96 Mbits (or 1.62 Mbytes) of information in eight minutes corresponds to a rate of 27 kbps. Again, we consider packet sizes of 8 bytes through 64 bytes in steps of 8 bytes for both sources. The aircraft is modeled as a stationary node that for eight minutes out of every thirty receives data from source 2 and for a separate eight minutes out of thirty transmits an equal amount of data to the destination. The worst case for end-to-end delay happens when the line-of-sight contact with the destination ends just prior to when the line-of-sight contact with source 2 begins. Thus, this is the situation we model. Source 2 sends data to the aircraft from 1400 to 1408 and from 1430 to 1438. The aircraft sends data to the destination from 1422 to 1430 and from 1452 to 1500.

Results

Tables 1-3 show the results from scenario 1. In Table 1 we list the total number of packets and bytes sent from each source for each packet size. Tables 2 and 3 respectively show the number of dropped packets at the router from source 1 and source 2.

From these tables we observe that source 1 loses from 1.99% to 5.88% of the packets it sends, depending on the mix of packet sizes. The best case occurs when packets from source 1 are 24 bytes long and packets from source 2 are 56 bytes long. For this mix, source 1 drops 5,713 packets (137,112 bytes) out of a total of 286,876 packets (6,885,024 bytes) sent. The worst case occurs when packets from source 1 are 8 bytes long and packets from source 2 are 16 bytes long. In this case, source 1 drops 50,572 packets (404,576 bytes) out of a total of 860,625 packets (6,885,000 bytes) sent.

Table 1: Amount of information sent by each source

Packet Size (bytes)	Source 1		Source 2	
	Packets	Bytes	Packets	Bytes
8	860625	6885000	405000	3240000
16	430313	6885008	202501	3240016
24	286876	6885024	135001	3240024
32	215157	6885024	101250	3240000
40	172126	6885040	81001	3240040
48	143438	6885024	67501	3240048
56	122947	6885032	57858	3240048
64	107579	6885056	50626	3240064

Table 2: Source 1 packets dropped at the router

Source 2 Packet Size (bytes)	Source 1 Packet Size (bytes)							
	8	16	24	32	40	48	56	64
8	45878	25272	8981	10823	8714	6117	5207	4495
16	50572	25265	8416	12616	10088	4482	7200	5399
24	25286	25261	16827	12609	10082	8397	4795	6291
32	50570	25260	16825	7315	10079	4196	5136	6288
40	50571	25259	16823	10376	9845	7864	6110	5090
48	34341	12630	16822	12605	8928	8366	3593	6281
56	50571	25258	5713	12604	7556	5592	7184	6281
64	50571	25257	16821	12603	10073	8387	7177	6280

Table 3: Source 2 packets dropped at the router

Source 2 Packet Size (bytes)	Source 1 Packet Size (bytes)							
	8	16	24	32	40	48	56	64
8	4699	1	23578	7216	6783	13770	14019	14503
16	0	0	12623	1	0	11765	0	3600
24	8429	0	0	3	1	1	5595	4
32	0	0	0	5293	0	6296	3596	1
40	0	0	0	1784	232	633	1508	1912
48	2705	4210	0	0	956	24	4191	3
56	0	0	4762	0	1799	2387	0	1
64	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0

Interestingly, there are quite a few configurations of packets sizes for which Source 2 does not lose any packets. However, the loss rates range from 0% to 8.23% of the packets it sends. The worst case for source 2 corresponds to the best case for source 1, when packets from source 1 are

24 bytes long and packets from source 2 are 56 bytes long. In this case, source 2 drops 4,762 packets (266,672 bytes) out of a total of 57,858 packets (3,240,048 bytes) sent.

Table 4 shows the total number of bytes lost from both sources for each packet size. The values in this table range from 401,920 to 404,616 bytes with an average of 403,451.75 bytes and a standard deviation of 753.48 bytes.

Table 4: Total bytes lost at the router

Source 2 Packet Size (bytes)	Source 1 Packet Size (bytes)							
	8	16	24	32	40	48	56	64
8	404616	404360	404168	404064	403904	403776	403744	403704
16	404576	404240	403952	403728	403520	403376	403200	403136
24	404584	404176	403848	403560	403304	403080	402800	402720
32	404560	404160	403800	403456	403160	402880	402688	402464
40	404568	404144	403752	403392	403080	402792	402480	402240
48	404568	404160	403728	403360	403008	402720	402376	402128
56	404568	404128	403784	403328	402984	402648	402304	402040
64	404568	404112	403704	403296	402920	402576	402232	401920

For scenario 2, all results were exactly as anticipated. Regardless of the mix of packet sizes, **with the NTO no packets were dropped from either source**. Also, all data sent from source 2 to the aircraft was subsequently sent from the aircraft to the final destination.

Conclusions

Although the scenarios described here are simple and the results are intuitive, the main conclusion is that decisions made with the assistance of an NTO could positively impact the overall QoS of the future GIG.

The current situation is one of local scope. With no other information, given the choice between a higher bandwidth route with small delay and a lower bandwidth route with large delay, the first choice seems obvious. It is a greedy choice in the sense that it appears to offer the best service for source 2. Having an NTO would allow one to see more globally in order to make the less obvious, but in the long run, better decision. The second option can be seen as the better choice for it allows the high-priority data from source 1 to flow uninterrupted, and all of the data from source 2 still reaches the destination in exchange for additional delay. Not only is source 2 sacrificing speed for the benefit of source 1, but source 2 also reaps the benefit of not losing any packets.

If we have a situation where ferrying delays for data from source 2 to the destination are not tolerable, then other

options could be explored. One option would be to increase the bandwidth on the links through the router. If that is not a feasible option, then perhaps a second router could be deployed. If the aircraft was not available, but delays are acceptable, then yet another option would be for source 2 to store its information during the period from 1400-1500 without transmitting it. At 1500, source 2 could then begin sending the stored information at an increased rate until it catches back up to live data. Finally, if the data from source 2 is of low enough priority, it may be suitable to simply turn off the data flow at 1400 and then turn it back on at 1500. Any data from that time period is just lost.

FUTURE WORK

As our research proceeds, we hope to build upon the scenarios in this article to make them more realistic. We also intend to determine more specifically the classes of data and directives that should be placed into the NTO. Also important is how to make the transition from a plan in the NTO to actual execution. Of particular interest is how to update the NTO in response to missions implemented on short notice or to real-time changes in mission plans.

SUMMARY

In order for the future GIG to enable NCW/NCO, it must incorporate dynamic H-MANETs that can respond rapidly to changing operational needs with a high QoS. By taking advantage of the highly planned nature of military operations, an NTO can be created in conjunction with an ATO to provide a basis for the network to predictively adapt in an attempt to optimize network performance and reliability. We have described at a high level the type of data that can be included in an NTO and some of the sources for that data, and provided a notional example of an ATO-NTO translation. While the concept of an NTO is not entirely new, we have not found any work that directly supports the claim that an NTO can improve QoS. We have given an example where a networking decision made at the tactical level in the absence of an NTO results in the loss of up to 5.88% of high-priority data. Presented the same choice under the clarifying light an NTO would provide, a decision is made at the operational level which allows all data to be transferred in exchange for some tolerable delay. An NTO will allow mission planning and network optimization beyond current capabilities.

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